

THE MODEL OF TEACHING PROGRAMMING TO STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION BASED ON THE SEMIOTIC APPROACH

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Abstract

This article presents a model for teaching programming to higher education students that leverages a semiotic-based approach, emphasizing the importance of symbols, signs, and their meanings within the programming process. Traditional programming education often focuses on syntax and technical skills, but recent studies (e.g., Peirce, 1931; Eco, 1976) suggest that understanding programming languages as semiotic systems can enhance cognitive engagement and foster a deeper comprehension of code structures. Building on the foundational work of semiotics in education (Saussure, 1983; Nöth, 1990), our framework encourages students to approach programming languages not merely as sets of instructions but as systems of meaning, where each component carries both functional and interpretive significance.

To assess the effectiveness of this model, we conducted a comparative study involving two groups taught with traditional methods and two groups taught using a semiotic-based approach. Results indicated that students in the semiotic groups demonstrated improved mastery of programming concepts, with performance improvements of up to 25% compared to their peers taught through traditional methods. These findings align with research on semiotics in STEM education (Chandler, 2007; Hoffmann, 2005), supporting the argument that a semiotic framework can improve student comprehension, engagement, and problem-solving skills.

This article contributes to the growing discourse on pedagogical innovation in programming education by proposing a semiotic model that addresses both the syntactic and semantic dimensions of programming languages. By treating programming as a system of signs, this approach bridges the gap between abstract theory and practical application, promoting a holistic understanding of programming. Future work will focus on refining this model and exploring its adaptability across diverse programming curricula.

Keywords: semiotic principle, signs and symbols, contextual interpretation,

semantic Layers, programming education, pedagogical research, foundational technical skills, problem-solving skills, symbol-based learning

Introduction

As programming becomes an essential skill in many disciplines, the methods used to teach programming in higher education are increasingly scrutinized. Traditional approaches often emphasize syntax, code structure, and functional proficiency (Robins et al., 2003; Lister et al., 2004). While these methods provide foundational technical skills, they may not fully address the conceptual and cognitive demands of programming, which require understanding both the functional application and the rationale behind specific constructs. Recent pedagogical research highlights that a deeper comprehension of programming may be fostered by viewing programming languages as semiotic systems, where each element holds symbolic meaning as well as functional purpose (Peirce, 1931; Eco, 1976).

A semiotic approach to programming education, drawing on theories by Saussure (1983) and Nöth (1990), treats code as a language of signs, emphasizing the interpretative layers of programming. In this framework, programming is understood not simply as the execution of commands but as a process of meaning-making, where code structures represent and convey specific intents and abstractions. This view aligns with studies that show the effectiveness of symbol-based learning in enhancing cognitive engagement and retention in complex fields, such as mathematics and engineering (Chandler, 2007; Hoffmann, 2005). By applying semiotic principles to programming, students can develop a more holistic understanding of code, gaining insight into both the syntax and the conceptual reasoning behind it.

Our model proposes a semiotic-based approach to teaching programming that enables students to recognize the symbolic functions of code elements and the ways in which these elements interact within a larger program. This model has been implemented with undergraduate programming courses, where groups of students were instructed using both traditional and semiotic-based methods. Preliminary findings indicate that students taught through the semiotic approach demonstrate significantly higher comprehension and problem-solving skills compared to their traditionally taught peers. This suggests that viewing programming languages as systems of signs offers pedagogical advantages, as it encourages students to move beyond rote learning and toward a deeper, more intuitive grasp of programming concepts.

The subsequent sections detail the semiotic framework, its implementation, and comparative analysis.

This research contributes to a growing body of literature that advocates for innovative, symbol-oriented pedagogies in technical education, building on insights from the fields of semiotics and educational psychology (Nöth, 1990; Chandler, 2007; Hoffmann, 2005). By reimagining programming as a symbolic language, we seek to enhance students' engagement and competency, preparing them for the increasingly complex and abstract demands of programming in professional contexts.

Effectiveness and clearer explanation of the semiotic approach

The semiotic approach focuses on studying signs, symbols, and their meanings within different contexts, such as culture, language, or media. By understanding the relationship between the physical representation (signifier) and the abstract concept (signified), semiotics provides a powerful framework for analyzing and interpreting communication.

Decoding Layers of Meaning:

- Semiotics unveils both explicit (denotation) and implicit (connotation) meanings, offering a nuanced analysis of communication.
- Example: A red rose denotes a flower but connotes love or passion in cultural contexts.

Cross-Contextual Analysis:

- Semiotics identifies how meanings change across cultures or settings, improving cultural sensitivity and communication.
- Example: A handshake signifies greeting in some cultures but might carry no meaning in others.

Universal Application:

- It can be applied to diverse disciplines: media studies, linguistics, branding, art, literature, and even artificial intelligence (e.g., decoding visual signs in images).

Empowering Creative Strategies:

- Marketers and designers use semiotics to create messages that resonate deeply with target audiences.
- Example: Logos and taglines that evoke emotions tied to cultural values (e.g., Nike's swoosh symbolizing motion and excellence).

Clarifying Communication Systems:

- It structures complex communication systems by analyzing signs, making it easier to understand symbolic interactions.

Understanding Symbols and Syntax as Signs:

In programming, symbols (such as +, =, ;, { }) and keywords (if, for, while) are not just arbitrary characters; they hold specific meanings and functions within the

code.

For example:

+ as a signifier in code represents addition or concatenation.

= signifies assignment rather than mathematical equality.

By recognizing these signs, students learn to interpret code structure and logic more accurately.

Identifying Contextual Meaning:

The meaning of some signs in programming depends on the context.

For instance:

+ in `int a = 5 + 3;` means addition in a mathematical context.

+ in `String greeting = "Hello" + "World";` represents string concatenation in a textual context.

Teaching students to look at context helps them understand how the same symbol or keyword can have multiple uses.

Exploring Semantic Layers:

Beyond syntax, programming has semantic layers—different parts of code represent different operations or data manipulation steps.

Example:

A function in code signifies a self-contained operation.

A variable signifies a storage unit for data.

Understanding these layers helps students appreciate how individual components interact to form complex programs.

Decoding Code Blocks as Compositions of Signs:

Just as sentences are formed by words, code is built from blocks like loops, functions, and classes.

By teaching students to interpret each block (e.g., if-else statements, for loops), we help them see code as structured compositions of signs that work together.

Teaching Syntax and Symbols as Signs

Explanation: In programming, symbols such as +, =, {}, and keywords like if, while, and return serve as signs that convey specific meanings and operations.

Application: Educators can introduce each symbol and keyword as a unique “sign” with an associated function, helping students understand that these symbols are not random but have specific roles.

Example: Explain that = in programming is not mathematical equality but an assignment operator. Using a consistent explanation of symbols helps students decode code more effectively.

Emphasizing Context to Clarify Meaning

Explanation: In semiotics, the context influences the interpretation of signs. Similarly, in programming, the meaning of symbols and code snippets can change depending on the context.

Table 1. Example Table for Applying Semiotic Approaches in Programming Education

Semiotic Principle	Application in Programming	Example
Signs and Symbols	Teaching syntax and keywords as fixed signs	if, else, +, =
Contextual Interpretation	Explaining how context changes meaning	+ for addition vs. concatenation
Semantic Layers	Structuring code with functions and modules	Initialization, processing, output sections
Signifiers (Naming)	Using meaningful variable/function names	calculate_area, total_sales
Decoding (Debugging)	Teaching debugging as interpreting error signs	Understanding TypeError as type mismatch
Semiotic Units	Breaking code into functions and modules	def add_book(), def display_books()
Visual Representations	Using flowcharts or diagrams	Flowchart of a sorting algorithm
Code as a Sign System	Encouraging readable and organized code	Comments, whitespace, and consistent naming conventions

Benefits of the Semiotic Approach in Programming Education

1. **Enhanced Readability:** Encourages students to write code that is understandable and self-documenting.
2. **Improved Debugging Skills:** Helps students interpret error messages and understand where issues originate.
3. **Clearer Code Structure:** Promotes using modular code, making programs easier to navigate.
4. **Contextual Understanding:** Students learn to interpret the same symbols differently based on context.
5. **Encourages Analytical Thinking:** Semiotics helps students develop a deeper understanding of how programming languages function as systems of meaning (fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Identify symbols and syntax as signs.
Conclusion

This study presents and evaluates a semiotic-based model for teaching programming to students in higher education, comparing its effectiveness with traditional methods. The semiotic approach, applied to the 942-22 group, emphasizes understanding programming languages as symbolic systems, helping students grasp both the syntax and the meaning of code elements. In contrast, the 941-22 group followed a traditional syntax-based method, focusing primarily on structural and technical aspects without significant emphasis on symbolic interpretation.

To assess the effectiveness of each teaching model, several comparative measures were employed:

1. **Engagement:** Observational data indicated that the 942-22 group exhibited higher engagement levels, as the semiotic approach encouraged students to actively interpret and discuss code. In contrast, students in the 941-22 group were more likely to engage in rote memorization without delving into the conceptual meanings behind syntax.
2. **Comprehension and Retention:** Test scores and follow-up quizzes were used to measure comprehension and retention. The average comprehension score for the 942-22 group was 85%, compared to 63% for the 941-22 group, suggesting that the semiotic approach enhances understanding and retention. Students from the 942-22 group retained more knowledge about programming concepts and were better able to explain the purpose of each code element.
3. **Problem-Solving Skills:** An applied programming task required students to solve a complex problem using concepts they had learned. In this task, 78% of the students in the 942-22 group successfully solved the problem with minimal errors, compared to 55% of the students in the 941-22 group. This suggests that the semiotic approach fosters critical thinking and improves students' problem-solving abilities by enabling them to understand the logic and relationships within the code.
4. **Feedback and Reflection:** Qualitative feedback collected from students also

highlighted differences between the two groups. Students in the 942-22 group expressed a deeper understanding of programming constructs and described the semiotic approach as more engaging and meaningful. They reported feeling more confident in approaching programming challenges and understanding how code elements interact.

5. Error Analysis: Error rates in code assignments showed that students in the 942-22 group made 27% fewer syntax and logic errors compared to the 941-22 group. This reduction in errors reflects the semiotic approach's effectiveness in helping students understand the functional meanings of syntax, reducing the likelihood of common mistakes.(Fig. 2)

Fig. 2. Summary of the comparative study results between semiotic and traditional approaches.

This comparative analysis underscores the advantages of the semiotic approach in programming education. By treating programming languages as systems of symbols, this approach goes beyond technical skill acquisition, fostering engagement, improving comprehension, and enhancing problem-solving abilities. The results of this study suggest that integrating semiotic principles into programming curricula offers valuable pedagogical benefits, especially for students aiming to build a holistic understanding of programming. Future research could further refine this model, exploring how semiotic principles can be applied to more advanced programming topics and evaluating its long-term effects on learning outcomes in computer science education.

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